

Great Mosque at Kilwa

also known as “Msikiti Mkuu wa Kilwa”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Arabic, Mosque, Religious Place, Language, Islam in Africa, Islamic Traditions, Sunni

The Great Mosque at Kilwa (Kis. Msikiti Mkuu wa Kilwa) is a congregational mosque on the island of Kilwa (Kilwa Kisiwani), currently located in Tanzania. It is important because it served as the most important mosque in the medieval city of Kilwa, the capital of the Sultanate of Kilwa (c.950-1505CE). Its origins likely lie in the 10th century CE, but multiple additions and renovations were made over the years as the sultanate grew more prosperous and in response to exigencies of maintenance. The northern prayer hall likely represents the earliest phase of construction (11th-12th cen. CE) and is composed of 16 bays supported by 9 pillars of coral and timber. The surviving structure of the mosque is one of coral limestone. The mosque currently lies in ruin, with many of its domes collapsed, but enough of the structure remains to indicate its size and features when in use. The mosque was modified in the 13th century CE, but major renovations took place in the 14th century CE under Sultan al-Hassan ibn Sulaiman (r.1310-1333CE). Al-Hassan added a southern extension capped by a huge dome, which was described by Ibn Battuta when he visited the city in 1331 CE. The vaulted ceilings and domes of the mosque are held aloft by coral limestone pillars. Ibn Battuta's descriptions of the mosque should be treated with caution, as he describes the mosque as constructed out of timber while archaeological evidence indicates that stone was used to construct the mosque as early as the 11th-12th centuries CE. The mosque is one of the largest mosques constructed during the medieval Swahili civilization (1100-1500CE). Other than its remarkable size, the mosque shares many features with other mosques constructed during the Swahili period. For instance, all Swahili mosques constructed during the medieval period, including the Great Mosque at Kilwa, were constructed out of coral rag held together with mud and lime mortar. The mosque was damaged by an earthquake in 1331, but its final ruination came about when renovations were attempted in the 18th century CE, leading to the partial collapse of its roof and its abandonment. The mosque lies in ruin to this day and serves as a major tourist attraction. Archaeological work has taken place around the mosque. More recently, the Zamani Project undertook to 3D scan and document the mosque.

Date Range: 950 CE - 1800 CE

Region: Kilwa Kisiwani

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania

The island of Kilwa, which served as the capital of the Sultanate of Kilwa (950-1505CE)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chittick, Neville (1963). "Kilwa and the Arab Settlement of the East African Coast". *The Journal of African History*. 4 (2): 179–190. doi:10.1017/S0021853700004011
- Source 2: Chittick, Neville (22 January 2009). "The 'Shirazi' Colonization of East Africa". *The Journal of African History*. 6 (3): 275–294. doi:10.1017/S0021853700005806
- Source 3: Pollard, Edward John (1 September 2008). "The maritime landscape of Kilwa Kisiwani and its region, Tanzania, 11th to 15th century AD". *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology*. 27 (3): 265–280. doi:10.1016/j.jaa.2008.07.001.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.arkeologi.uu.se/digitalAssets/483/c_483244-l_3-k_suttonrevised1.pdf
- Source 1 Description: The southern Swahili harbour and town on Kilwa island, 800-1800 AD: a chronology of booms and slumps
- Source 2 URL: <https://zamaniproject.org/site-tanzania-kilwa-kisiwani.html#header5-bd>
- Source 2 Description: Zamani Project - Kilwa Kisiwani

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Scientific archaeological surveys have been conducted by Chittick, Sutton, Fleisher, and Pollard.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1960-present

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: No official name

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: The mosque is located near the coast/shore on the island of Kilwa Kisiwani

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: A well

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was an important feature of the city of Kilwa when it was occupied. The city and the mosque lie in ruins now.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The current setting is rural, but the past setting was urban

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: There is a ferry that brings people from the mainland to the island and there are well-trodden paths on the island itself leading to the mosque and other important structures on the island.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The mosque is located in what would have been the city of Kilwa, the capital of the Kilwa Sultanate.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was part of the city of Kilwa, which included other mosques as well.

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Shore, ocean, freshwater well

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque is the largest of 6-8 mosques that served the city of Kilwa at its height.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: Communal and individual worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: Communal Muslim worship, although worship could take place by individuals if needed

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was constructed out of coral limestone and intended to last as long as possible

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The mosque was initially constructed in the 950s CE (we think). Major expansions took place in the 11th/12th centuries. Sultan al-Hasan ibn Sulaiman added a domed southern extension in the early 14th century. Expansions were attempted in the 1700s, which led to the partial collapse and ruination of the mosque and thus its abandonment.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: Expansions were attempted in the 1700s, which led to the partial collapse of the roof and part of the structure. The mosque was then abandoned.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: It collapsed accidentally as a result of attempted repairs in the 18th century CE.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

– Other [specify]: The mosque accidentally collapsed when renovations were attempted in the 18th century CE.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: The initial construction of the mosque took place likely in the 950s. The mosque was expanded in the 11th/12th century CE, but a major expansion and construction of a

large dome took place in the early 14th century under Sultan al-Hasan ibn Sulaiman. Attempted expansion in the 18th century CE led to the accidental collapse and abandonment of the mosque.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: Attempted renovations in the 18th century CE led to the accidental collapse of a part of the mosque and many of its smaller domes. The mosque was thence abandoned.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The mosque is dedicated to Allah

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Council of elders

– King or emperor

Notes: The mosque was built and expanded by the Sultans of Kilwa. Its earliest construction phase dates to the time of the establishment of the Sultanate of Kilwa in the 950s CE. Expansions took place in the 11th/12th centuries, but a major expansion that involved the construction of a large dome took place under Sultan al-Hasan ibn Sulaiman in the early 14th century CE. A few centuries after the fall of the Sultanate, local leaders at Kilwa attempted to

expand the mosque, leading to its accidental collapse and consequent abandonment.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, given the history of the region, both free and unfree labor were used to construct the mosque. However, this remains unknown.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We don't know why that particular spot was chosen for the construction of the Great Mosque of Kilwa

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The earliest construction phases of the mosque seem to coincide with the establishment of the Sultanate of Kilwa. Thus, the mosque may have been built because of the establishment of the Sultanate.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Kilwa was a wealthy trading city, so presumably local magnates themselves sponsored the construction of the mosque as an act of piety.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: Like other mosques, the Great Mosque at Kilwa was likely constructed as an act of piety intended to curry divine favor.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Quran

Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As the mosque is currently in ruins, we don't know where religious texts were stored within the structure.

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Yes

↳ Are they read aloud:

– Yes

↳ To a human audience

– Yes

Notes: The Quran was likely read out to a human audience when the mosque was in use.

↳ Are they studied:

– Yes

Notes: Most likely, the mosque served as a religious school as well.

↳ Are they recopied:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Used for divination:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: The history of the use of religious texts on the Swahili coasts remains something of a mystery.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The mosque itself serves as a monumental structure

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 100

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: To my knowledge, the mosque has not been measured

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Beach sand was likely used in the construction of the mosque

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes
Notes: Mud mortar was used in the construction of the mosque

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes
Notes: Lime plaster was produced on the island, as it is today, for construction purposes.
The mosque is plastered over with white lime plaster.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Timber was used for the construction of the mosque, but from where this timber was sourced remains unknown.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: The mosque is constructed out of local coral limestone

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: None

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

Notes: Geometric designs like squares and cross-hatches are present inside and outside the structure.

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– I don't know

Notes: Movable reliefs or tapestries may have been used in the Great Mosque of Kilwa, but its abandonment makes it difficult to tell one way or another.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

Notes: In accordance with Islamic practice, no figural decoration is present.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Geometric shapes like squares, diamonds, and cross-hatches are present

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– I don't know

Notes: Writing on perishable materials may have been present, but the ruination and abandonment of the mosque makes it difficult to say.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: None

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

Notes: No figural representations are present in the Great Mosque of Kilwa

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone,

clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Geometric reliefs are present in the form of carved squares, diamonds, and cross-hatches.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Paintings and other movable art may have been present in the mosque when it was in use

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Geometric designs like squares, diamonds, and cross-hatches.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Burials are associated with the mosque. A sultan may be buried in the mosque, but this remains

only a rumor.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: A cemetery is associated with the mosque

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque is associated with Muslim prayer. However, given the syncretic nature of Swahili Islam, other "lesser" beings may have been considered to be present.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: Divination could have taken place at this place or in some place associated with it. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of previously human spirits at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of previously human spirits and their communication with the living at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of nonhuman supernatural beings at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of nonhuman supernatural beings and their communication with the living at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of mixed human-divine beings at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of mixed human-divine beings and their communication with humans at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: No representation of Allah is present in this mosque

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the presence of supernatural monitoring at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the communication of the living with gods or supernatural beings at places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Large scale Muslim rituals likely took place

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Individual worship likely took place at the Great Mosque of Kilwa

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown. The mosque could accommodate 1000-2000 people at most, but its abandonment makes it difficult to say exactly how many people attended large-scale rituals

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: These rituals presumably took place in accordance with Muslim theology

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude orthodoxy checks, but the effectiveness of these remains unknown. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude orthopraxy checks, but the effectiveness of these remains unknown. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam likely included synchronic practices. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude the use of intoxicants in religious practice, especially given the role played by palm wine in the medieval period, when the mosque was active. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude sacrifice at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately. However, I would suggest that given common Muslim practice, this is unlikely.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude self-sacrifice at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately. However, I would suggest that given common Muslim practice, this is unlikely.

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude offerings at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately. However, I would suggest that given common Muslim practice, this is unlikely.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Notes: The mosque is now abandoned, and the only maintenance is conducted by the antiquities authorities of Tanzania. Given the periodic renovations and expansions that are part of the mosque's history and given its long use as a place of worship, one must presume that the mosque was regularly maintained at least until the collapse of the Sultanate of Kilwa, if not until the 18th-century collapse of the mosque itself.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Notes: Given the size of the Great Mosque and the importance of Kilwa, it is plausible that the Great Mosque served as a pilgrimage point.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude feasting at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Yearly festivals such as those marking the onset of the month of Ramadan, Eid al-adha and Eid al-fitr, and Maulidi could have taken place in or around the mosque

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Notes: Given current Muslim practice, all members of society would have participated in religious festivals held at or around the mosque

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude festivals serving as defining elements in the construction/decoration of places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Given the large size of the mosque, it could have easily accommodated 1000-2000 people

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Notes: Muslim festivals are generally marked by feasting. Assuming this was the case in the past, festivals associated with the Great Mosque of Kilwa may have associated with feasting as well.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

Notes: Muslim festivals are generally marked by feasting. Assuming this was the case in the past, festivals associated with the Great Mosque of Kilwa may have associated with feasting as well.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude divination taking place at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The syncretic nature of Swahili Islam does not preclude healing taking place at or near places of worship. The abandonment of the mosque and the lack of texts describing religious practice in this mosque makes it difficult to answer this question accurately.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: The mosque is currently abandoned. Presumably, when it was in use, a dedicated religious specialist like an Imam was in charge of this important mosque.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Notes: The Great Mosque may have served as a school/training facility when it was in use, but this is no longer the case after its abandonment in the 18th century.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The antiquities authorities of Tanzania are currently in charge of the maintenance of the Great Mosque. Formal institutions may have existed for the maintenance of the Great Mosque when it was in use.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Notes: The mosque was abandoned in the 18th century and lies in ruin. A formal bureaucracy may have been associated with the mosque when it was in use.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Notes: The mosque was abandoned in the 18th century and lies in ruin. The Great Mosque may have controlled economic resources when it was in use.

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque was abandoned in the 18th century and lies in ruin. Public works and services may have been associated with the mosque when it was in use.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque was abandoned in the 18th century and lies in ruin. Non-religious writings (like accounts) may have been stored in the mosque when it was in use.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Quran is associated with every mosque, and the Great Mosque was no exception.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– I don't know

Notes: Swahili epics may have been associated with this place during the medieval period.

However, the abandonment of the mosque and the lack of descriptions of its activities when it was in use make this question difficult to answer.

Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– I don't know

Notes: The foundation of the city of Kilwa itself is associated with the Kilwa Chronicle.

Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Not since the abandonment of the mosque, but imams would likely have interpreted the Quran for lay worshippers when the mosque was in use.

Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– I don't know

Notes: Current Swahili Muslim practice involves inserting pieces of paper with Quranic verses between bricks/stones when a building is being constructed. The antiquity of this practice and whether it took place during the construction of the Great Mosque of Kilwa remain unknown.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Great Mosque at Kilwa, Chittick, Neville. "Kilwa and the Arab Settlement of the East African Coast" 4, no. 2 (July 1963). <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0021853700004011>.

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